

ISic3473

I.Sicily inscription 3473

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

local stone

Object

column capital

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

S. Marco d'Alunzio, Cathedral, left aisle of the Cathedral, a broken capital

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Cathedral

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336066

1. [Σ(?)]ιμούλου
2. [Κ]αλλιππίδα.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644942

EDCS 70900809

PHI 336066

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1272

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 42 no.22 fig.97

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